

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION		STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT		 University of Sheffield School of Archaeology Gabii Project	
				Min: 62.041	Max: 62.375	1465	<input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic		
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 2019-51		Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #:		
DEFINITION fill of sewer cut				Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 0		Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1464		Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition						
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are						SOIL/MATRIX			
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		clay 20% silt 33% sand %			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery f <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles f <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Dolia f <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) medium <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones r <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cohesive			
						Compaction		Color	
						<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft		<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)									
Northern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original			
Southern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
Western Limit			<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
Eastern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE									
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry):					
Is abutted by:				Abuts: 1385					
Is covered by: 0				Covers: 1001					
Is cut by:				Cuts:					
Is filled by:				Fills: 1464					
OBSERVATIONS very rocky at top of fill. Much deeper than adjacent sewer fill 1385.									
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: southern, central Shape: roughly rectangular									
For layers complete this section:									
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): slopes south east									
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) very rocky, some tufo									
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): decreases the deeper one gets									
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commigled <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> other (specify) bed rock									
For cuts complete this section:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):					
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight									
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping									
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular									
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded									
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded									
Observations:									

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Free of sewer cut into bedrock.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

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